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A Project-Based ICT Education by Citizen Support System Development

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ABSTRACT

One of the difficulties in ICT education in regular lessons is that educators must teach all the techniques for developing systems within a limited time frame, despite the fact that students cannot learn without actually experiencing the various techniques. This paper introduces an educational method of software development that is collaboration between the industry and the community. The method is based on the principles of Project-Based Learning (PBL). The proposed method features learning software development technology by incorporating an actual citizen support system using the Spiral model [1]. The project was supported as one of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications IoT Service Creation Support Project. The purpose of the IoT Service Creation Support Project is to identify specific problems that should be overcome when creating and deploying IoT services through demonstration projects, build a reference model that will help solve the issues, and promote data utilization etc. In addition, it is to play a leading role lead to the development and maintenance of the necessary rules for the IoT service. Students developed a citizen support system. Through this activity students learned about the idea of entrepreneurship. By use of the developing system and prototype system for citizens, as well as from the results of responses to a questionnaire survey, we found that the method developed is effective for improving citizen life.

Conference Key Areas: University-Business cooperation, “I want to contribute to solve local problems”, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: ICT, Industry-academia collaboration, Software engineering, Project-Based-Learning

INTRODUCTION

ICT education is difficult to deliver in a regular classroom setting because of the need to introduce all the techniques for developing systems in a limited amount of time. In addition, it is impossible to teach students practical requirements analysis, architectural design, etc., in such a limited time frame. The primary reason this is not possible is the inability to teach such techniques without actually having experienced them.

This paper introduces an educational method of software development that collaborates with industry and community. The method is based on Project-Based Learning (PBL) and applied to the students of the Department of Information and Computer Science in Kanazawa Institute of Technology (KIT). The method features a learning software development technology by creating an actual citizen support system using the Spiral model [1]. The software development method, using the Spiral model, is compatible with the Project Design Program in KIT [2].

The project was supported as one of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications IoT Service Creation Support Project. The purpose of the IoT Service Creation Support Project is to identify specific problems that should be overcome when creating and deploying IoT services through demonstration projects, build a reference model that will help solve the issues, and promote data utilization etc. In addition, it is to play a leading the role lead to the development and maintenance of the necessary rules for the IoT service. The group of Nonoichi City, NEC Solutions Innovator Co., Ltd., Yoshida Advertising Co., Ltd., Kanazawa Institute of Technology and Kanazawa Technical College was selected for this project.

This paper explains in detail the practical project that was carried out in Nonoichi-City. The city, located in Ishikawa Prefecture in Japan, requested the development of the ICT system for citizen support. We carried out an educational project in which the students themselves thought about a given problem and methods of problem-solving by collaborating with companies and the city. In an effort to solve the given problem, we developed an information terminal bus stop and submitted proposals to Nonoichi-City. The developed system comprised five sub-systems: Timetable and Transfer Guidance System, Children's and Elderly's Observation System, Disaster Countermeasure System, Advertisement System, and City Public Relations System. This system features image recognition software and provides service matching for each individual.

From active engagement with the project, students learned how to listen to individual requests, analyze the requests, and create the system. In addition, they also learned how to conduct the operational test, solve extraction problems, and improve the system. The project allowed students to receive hands-on education, and at the same time, also had favorable effects on the community. In fact, when using the prototype system for the citizens and conducting a questionnaire survey, we received numerous comments on its effectiveness in improving citizen life.

This paper is organized in the following manner. First, we explain the KIT Education system. Second, we present the intended characteristics of an ICT education in collaboration with Nonoichi City. The educational method of software development using PBL and the Spiral model is addressed in detail. Third, we explain their effects. Lastly, we offer a summary of the material presented.

1 SIGNIFICANCE OF PROJECT ACTIVITIES IN KIT

In KIT, students are educated in two wheels of curricular education and extracurricular education (Fig. 1). The Project Design Program (PD) is the backbone of the curricular education, it is carried out as a regular class for all students and has made great progress [2-3]. Project-Based Learning (PBL) is applied in PD courses.

Extracurricular activities also play an important role in KIT. They include YUMEKOBO Projects (YUMEKOBO is a Japanese term which refers to the Factory for Dreams and Ideas), Department/Lab-related Programs, Collaboration Programs with Industry and Community[4], and Internship Programs. In these activities, students can set up objectives by themselves and learn from the successes and failures. For example, YUMEKOBO Projects are self-directed projects to develop students' technical competence [5]. There were 16 YUMEKOBO Projects in 2016 [6]. The education project described in this paper worked as an extracurricular activity.

Fig. 1. KIT Pedagogical System

Fig. 2 shows the problem solving flow used in PD education at KIT. In PD education, students learn the flow of the discovery of the problem, clarification of the problems, creation of ideas, selection of ideas, and implementation of the idea. In addition, even in extracurricular activities students will use the same flow to solve problems. The difference between the regular curriculum classes and the extracurricular projects is that the flow is carried out repeatedly in the extracurricular projects.

Fig. 2. Problem solving, improvement activities flow

In extracurricular activities, by repeating the improvement flow, students examine deep and complex matters. Students form a team with different grade levels unlike classes and execute the project. One benefit of working as a team consisting of different grade levels is that senior students are able to develop leadership skills. In addition, conducting the project allowed juniors to learn the importance of the regular curriculum classes.

2 DETAILS OF THE CITIZEN SUPPORT PROJECT ACTIVITIES

2.1 Project Objectives

Society is constantly changing. We believe that we need the ability to respond flexibly to this change. We also believe that the ability to create new value challenging and leading society in a better direction is important. We actively work on society's problems, improve society and think that the university's mission is to produce human resources that support the country. We are engaged in entrepreneurship education using the development of regional innovation system.

We believe that the three requirements for becoming a global leader are as follows, and we aim that students master these abilities. In the field of information processing, especially the change is intense, we felt that training of following skills is necessary, and decided to teach them through by the project activities.

- A) Awareness / understanding of shifting trends and needs in society
- B) Connect one's interests an/or abilities
- C) The mentality and action to make full use of one's resources and solve social challenges

We decided to work on improvement of citizen's life, targeting a city with a university. We thought that it was meaningful for students who are citizens to solve the problems owned by them and to enrich the lives of citizens. We decided to develop a citizen support system to solve the city's problems and enrich the lives of citizens.

The other purpose of the citizen support project is to nurture software development abilities and to develop problem solving skills of students by developing an ICT system for citizen support. We aim to improve the student's skill as an information processing engineer by educating system design method while actually creating the system, which is difficult to teach in the outcome. In addition, the system we developed was designed based on the five-year plan issued by the Nonoichi-City so as to contribute to the revitalization of the city and the improvement of citizen's living. With the cooperation of Nonoichi-City, this project carried out many activities. In addition, we also received the cooperation with local companies in developing the system.

We aim to establish a system that transcends the mere extracurricular activities of students, and can actually be used in society, and that can operate in the long term and moisturize society. It aims not only to construct a system but also to manufacture a bus stop of an information terminal and to construct a mechanism which can actually be used as a citizen support system. This includes monetary aspects including maintenance. It is a great significance for students to consider and construct a system that can actually be commercialized. In addition, if the system has social significance, we think that its significance will be greater.

First of all, the project had done the discovery of the problem, clarification of the problem. In the discovery of the problem and clarification of the problem, we conducted based on Nonoichi City's five-year plan published by Nonoichi City. We addressed the following five problems to be resolved within a 5-year plan of Nonoichi-City. The correspondence division of Nonoichi-City is also shown below.

- I. Timetable and Transfer Guidance ⇒ Area Promotion Section
- II. Watch over of Children ⇒ Child-Rearing Support Section
- III. Watch over of the Elderly ⇒ Regional Comprehensive Support Center
- IV. Disaster Countermeasures ⇒ Environmental Safety Division
- V. Advertisement and City Publicity ⇒ Secretary Public Relations Section

One of the more obvious characteristics of Nonoichi-City is that all of the 112 bus stops are consistently designed in the small city as 3 km in length and 3 km in width. The character named "Notty" is popular in Nonoichi-City, and this character is also used for the bus. Therefore, we tried to solve the problems that Nonoichi-City had, by making the information terminal bus stop which was shaped like a "Notty".

2.2 Flow of System Development

For the development of the system, students from the first year to the fourth grade of the university organized a team. It is a project of about twenty students. Within the project, system design and development were shared and carried out with a flexible group structure. In addition to the students, the project was conducted with four professors and two administrative staff members.

Fig. 3. Matching event of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications Hokuriku

Since finding the problem and clarification of the problem was completed, students created the idea. As the ideas were completed, students submitted the ideas to the G space matching event hosted by Hokuriku of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, and we were awarded the Grand Prix. After that, Students developed a system specification from an idea, and led to their creation of a prototype system. The Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications Hokuriku hosted a matching event with companies that supported the commercialization of the information terminal bus stop. We participated in a matching event and introduced the prototype system. Fig. 3 shows the situation of the matching event. Students were explaining about the system to companies. Thanks to this event, we found a

company willing to cooperate in its commercialization. Subsequently, we developed prototype improvement activities in collaboration with companies as well as Nonoichi-City.

The system we created to solve the problem consists of the following five subsystems.

- I. Timetable and Transfer Guidance System
- II. Children's and Elderly's Observation System
- III. Disaster Countermeasure System
- IV. Advertisement System
- V. City public relations System

The Information terminal bus stop has built-in Android terminal using the 3G network.

2.3 Interaction between Spiral Model and Problem Solving Procedure of KIT

The Waterfall model refers to a development model that gradually advances each development phase from system requirement definition to design, manufacturing and testing[7]. The Spiral Model is a technique to gradually expand the function by creating the main program and incorporating user's request[1]. Agile is one of the development methods to minimize risk by adopting a short development period unit called "iteration", meaning "quick", "agile"[8]. Each has its own strengths and weaknesses, and many Japanese companies are developing by Waterfalls model.

In the developing of the citizen support project, we selected the Spiral model. The merit of the Spiral model is that it is easy to reflect feedback and respond flexibly even when there is a problem regarding specification change from to feedback after trial use. As a result of repairing and repairing problems repeatedly, it is possible to finally create a quality system. We had to fix the system again and again, and it takes time to develop, but we thought that it would be good for students to wear skills slowly. Also, development could be done at the development pace that suit their abilities.

In utilizing the Spiral model, students were able to learn software development methods. In addition, the problem-solving flow adopted by KIT has much in common with the Spiral model, working together effectively and complementing each other. For example, if problems were found in the prototype, they were identified and solutions were devised. Based those discussions, solutions were developed and systemized. Since the Spiral Model is specifically designed to develop a system incrementally, it is easy to actualize the ideas through the programming.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To better determine the impact and potential success of the system we created, we conducted a questionnaire survey among 50 citizens concerning the prototype of the information terminal bus stop within the bus-stop waiting area. Fig. 4 illustrates students conducting of the questionnaire survey.

One question concerned the "necessity of the information terminal bus stop." As a result, thirty respondents answered that such an informational terminal was "necessary." When asked why this was needed, 19 people answered that it was effective for improving the convenience of public transportation. In addition, 10

people responded that it would contribute to the safety of the local society. Another 9 individuals responded that they expected regional vitalization to occur as a result of providing information about the city to citizens. The responses to this survey are evidence that our system is expected to improve convenience of public transportation as well as provide effective regional vitalization and improve city safety.

Fig. 4 Demonstration of information terminal bus stop and questionnaire survey

Through the development of the information terminal bus stop, students conducted the request analysis, learned the techniques needed to build the system, and the request from the city and its citizens were satisfied. In addition, they learned the method of operation testing, extraction of the problem, and problem-solving skills.

Such hands-on, real-life interactions are important because students do not have the chance to experience in the regular curriculum classes. The knowledge that students gained as a result of this research has the potential to help society as a whole because of the skills they develop while participating in it. Students taught with respect to one another in the same school year and learned together. Throughout this educational project, students developed abilities required within society. For example, seniors gained leadership skills while they, and other project members, improved communication skills and acquired an understanding of cooperative learning as well as a sense of responsibility.

Do you think that it is necessary to convert bus stops into information terminal bus stop?

Fig. 5. Questionnaire Result 1

In what purpose is the information terminal bus stop useful?

Fig. 6. Questionnaire Result 2

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper introduced the educational method of software development that encompasses the collaboration of industry and community. The method is based on Project-Based-Learning (PBL) and features learning software development technology by developing an authentic citizen support system using the Spiral model [1]. The project was supported as one of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications IoT Service Creation Support Project. The purpose of the IoT Service Creation Support Project is to identify specific problems that should be overcome when creating and deploying IoT services through demonstration projects, build a reference model that will help solve the issues, and promote data utilization etc. In addition, it is to play a leading the role lead to the development and maintenance of the necessary rules for the IoT service. As a result of using the prototype system for the citizens and conducting a questionnaire survey, it is clear that our system can work to improve citizen life.

When implementing this bus stop project, we were supported by the industry-university cooperation office in KIT. We are very grateful to the member of the industry-university cooperation office. In addition, we are very grateful to those in Nonoichi-City that worked with us.

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